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DEVELOPMENT, IMPLEMENTATION, AND EVALUATION OF A PEER-LED
SMOKING CESSATION SUPPORT GROUP

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

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DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Smoking is the leading preventable cause of death in the United States. Lynwood, California, where this QI project is conducted, is a high-risk, medically underserved community. Smoking is prevalent within Lynwood and residents are disproportionately affected by tobacco-related diseases such as lung cancer, COPD, and coronary artery disease. This community did not have a smoking cessation program. The aim of this QI project was to develop, implement, and evaluate the effectiveness of a peer-led smoking cessation support group (SCSG) within the high-risk community of Lynwood. The PRECEDE-PROCEED model, a community-oriented framework, was used to structure and guide the project. The project was implemented in four phases; recruitment of PCs, training of PCs, recruitment of participants, and finally conducting the peer-led SCSG.

Six PCs were recruited from a local faith-based organization and attended eight training sessions conducted by a tobacco treatment specialist. Smoking related topics were incorporated into classroom education including reflections, Motivational Interviewing and role play exercises. Peer coaches' leadership skills were evaluated with a competency checklist and their reflections on the entire experience were explored during telephone interviews. The PCs were able to successfully facilitate the SCSG. Four reflection themes were discovered including identification and reflections on their own addictions(s), feeling empowered with knowledge and skills to help their community, a

need for more time to build trust with participants, and describing their participation in this project as positive.

Five participants were recruited from the local community and participated in the peer-led SCSG for four weeks. Participants' readiness for change was measured with the readiness ruler, cigarette usage was self-reported with a two-item questionnaire, and perceived social support was measured with the Multidisciplinary Scale of Perceived Social Support. Four participants indicated a readiness to change and perceived increased social support at the end of the SCSG. They were also able to reduce the number of cigarettes smoked every week by 30 cigarettes at the end of the SCSG.

This project emphasized the importance of employing peer coaches to lead smoking cessation services in high-risk communities. Considering future opportunities for non-licensed providers to provide preventative health education services and incorporating PCs into smoking cessation programs is especially feasible in high-risk areas where resources are limited.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT	iii
LIST OF TABLES	viii
LIST OF FIGURES	ix
ACKNOWLEDGMENTS	x
BACKGROUND	1
Significance of the Project	1
Project Purpose	4
Conceptual Framework	4
Phase One: Social Diagnosis	6
Phase Two: Epidemiological Diagnosis	6
Phase Three: Behavioral/Environmental Diagnoses	7
Phase Four: Educational/Organizational Diagnosis	7
Phase Five: Administration Policy Assessment	8
Phase Six: Implementation	8
Phase Seven through Nine: Process/Impact and Outcome Evaluation	8
REVIEW OF LITERATURE	11
Literature Appraisal	12
Overview	16
Smoking Cessation Barriers and Motivation	18
Combined Treatment Approaches	20
Social Support Impact on Smoking Cessation	21
Limitations	23
Conclusion	25
METHODS	27
Current Practices	27
Design and Setting	27
Project Author Background and Qualifications	28
Sample	28
Peer Coaches	29

Smokers	29
Ethical Issues	29
Data Collection	30
Evaluation Checklist	30
Smoking History Questions.....	31
Readiness Ruler	32
Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support.....	32
Implementation.....	33
Phase One: Recruitment	34
Phase Two: Training of Peer Coaches	34
Phase Three: Recruitment of Smokers.....	35
Phase Four: Conducting the Smoking Cessation Support Group.....	36
 DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS	 38
Sociodemographic Characteristics of Peer Coaches.....	38
Evaluation of Peer Coaches.....	39
Qualitative Data about the Peer Coaching Experience	39
Sociodemographic Characteristics of Smoker Participants	41
Readiness of Smokers to Quit Smoking	41
Perception of Social Support.....	43
 DISCUSSION	 44
Peer Coaches	44
Participants in the Smoking Cessation Support Group.....	47
 PROJECT STRENGTH AND LIMITATIONS.....	 52
 FUTURE IMPLICATIONS FOR PRACTICE.....	 53
 CONCLUSION	 56
 REFERENCES.....	 57
 APPENDIX A: DATABASE SEARCH TOPICS	 75
 APPENDIX B: IMMIGRATION CENTER LETTER OF PERMISSION	 76
 APPENDIX C: READINESS RULER	 77
 APPENDIX D: COMMUNITY REFERRAL	 78
 APPENDIX E: SMOKING HISTORY	 79
 APPENDIX F: PEER COACH EVALUATION	 80

APPENDIX G: MULTIDIMENSIONAL SCALE OF PERCEIVED SOCIAL SUPPORT	81
APPENDIX H: SMOKING CESSATION SUPPORT GROUP FLYER	82

LIST OF TABLES

<u>Table</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. Initial Search Strategy.....	12
2. Training Topics	37
3. Peer Coach Demographics	38
4. Participant Demographics	42

LIST OF FIGURES

<u>Figure</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. PRECEDE-PROCEED model.....	5
2. Factors that influence health related behaviors	9
3. Project phases	33

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BACKGROUND

Cigarettes are highly addictive and habit forming. These factors make it difficult for people to stop smoking. The addiction potential of cigarettes is comparable to injectable heroin (American Heart Association [AHA], 2018). The agent of addiction in cigarettes is nicotine, which is delivered through inhalation. It should be noted that there are thousands of other chemicals inhaled along with nicotine, including 70 known carcinogens (American Cancer Society [ACA], 2017; AHA, 2018). Although cigarette smoking is addictive, harmful, and costly, the World Health Organization [WHO], (2018) estimated that 22.5% (one billion) of adult's smoke tobacco worldwide. Various methods to aid smokers in quitting have been developed; research is limited in identifying a method that combines medication, behavioral strategies, and social support.

Smoking disproportionately affects the poor, with more than 80% of smokers living in low- and middle-income countries (WHO, 2018). Despite efforts to reduce cigarette smoking in the U.S., 15.5% of adults (37.8 million people) and 4.1% of youths continue to smoke (WHO, 2017). In the U.S., 3,200 people smoke their first cigarette by the age of 18 (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2018). While the overall number of smokers varies by state, 12.2% of adults and 13.6% of youths in California are currently smoking (ACS, 2018). Within the Lynwood community, located in Los Angeles County, 13% of the population are current smokers (LACDPH, 2017).

Significance of the Project

There are significant morbidity and mortality associated with cigarette usage. Smoking is implicated in causing various cancers, heart disease, lung disease, and diabetes (CDC, 2018). Smoking also increases the risk of eye diseases and immune

system problems (CDC, 2018). Tobacco abuse will kill up to half of those who continue to smoke into middle age (WHO, 2018). Annually, tobacco causes six million deaths globally, and 480,000 deaths within the U.S. (CDC, 2018). In addition to its impact on health, smoking is costly to the individual, family, and society. The financial burden of cigarette smoking costs the U.S. more than \$300 billion dollars annually, mainly due to health care costs and loss of work productivity (CDC, 2018).

The increased morbidity and mortality caused by smoking are preventable. There are documented benefits to quitting smoking as early as possible. Most importantly, quitting smoking increases the former smoker's life expectancy and reduces the risk of death by 90%, if cessation occurs before the age of 40 (Jha et al., 2013). The most effective methods of quitting smoking include a combination of pharmacological and behavioral therapies (Stead, Koilpillai, Fanshaw, & Lancaster, 2016). However, even with recommended combined therapy methods, only 15.7%-35% will be successful in quitting (Stead et al., 2016). Therefore, improved smoking cessation strategies are needed. Programs with higher levels of social support have shown greater quit rates, and studies indicate that smokers prefer services that take place within their community, such as a church or community center, rather than a clinic (O'Keefe et al., 2018).

Lynwood is located within Los Angeles County and borders Paramount, South Gate, Compton, and Willowbrook. This community is predominately Hispanic (88%), with 38.2% of its residents foreign-born, most commonly from Mexico (LACDPH, 2018). Many residents are not citizens, with only 75.2 % of the community of Lynwood being U.S. citizens (LACDPH, 2018).

In comparison to the rest of California, residents of Lynwood live six fewer years, have lower incomes, and are less likely to graduate high school than residents of other cities (LACDPH, 2018). Within Lynwood, 47% of residents hold less than a high school degree, compared with 23% of other places inside Los Angeles County. Poverty is common, with 59% of residents living below 200% of the federal poverty level [FPL]. Smoking is prevalent within Lynwood, with 13% of the population being current smokers. The tobacco-related diseases are common among Lynwood residents, and the city is disproportionately affected by lung cancer, COPD, and coronary artery disease (LACDPH, 2018).

Lynwood is designated as a medically underserved area (Health Resource and Service Administration, 2020). Saint Francis Medical Center has 384 beds and is the only hospital located in the city of Lynwood (Saint Francis Medical Center, 2019). The hospital has been struggling financially and the parent company filed for bankruptcy in 2018 (Los Angeles Times, 2018). A recent community assessment identified the need for a smoking cessation program in Lynwood (Saint Francis Medical Center, 2019). However, low insurance reimbursement rates for tobacco cessation services disincentivize those wanting to start a cessation program. Medicare rates in 2019 reimbursed providers \$12.63 for three to ten minutes and \$26.71 for greater than ten minutes (Coding Intel, 2020).

California collaborated with national, state, and local public health officials to develop a single measure that summarizes the health of its communities, entitled the California Health Place Index [HPI]. Lynwood was found to be within the 14 percentile

in the HPI, meaning it has fewer healthy community conditions than other communities inside California (LACDPH, 2018).

A recent community needs assessment conducted by the local hospital in Lynwood, did not identify an evidenced-based program specifically to help smokers quit, although 12.5% of those within their service area are current smokers (Saint Francis Medical Center, 2019). The recent needs assessment was the motivation for the development of a smoking cessation program in this community.

Project Purpose

The purpose of this project was to develop, implement, and evaluate the effectiveness of a peer-led group for current smokers within the community of Lynwood. The peer-led support group aimed to increase social support, education, break habits linked to smoking, and increase coping mechanisms for smokers within the community. Community smoking cessation programs led by peer coaches (PCs) are successful in diverse high-risk populations (Barcelona de Mendoza & Damio, 2018). Cessation efforts were done through a combination of pharmacological, behavioral, and social support at a local church within the community. The project's end goal was to help smokers quit so that they may achieve an improved quality of life, not limited by tobacco.

Conceptual Framework

For this project, the PRECEDE-PROCEED model (see Figure 1) was used as the conceptual framework to develop, implement, and evaluate the effectiveness of a peer-led group for current smokers, within the community of Lynwood. The framework provided structure and helped guide the design, implementation, and evaluation of the project. A health program is a thoughtfully designed set of activities executed systematically to

accomplish health-related objectives (Green & Kreuter, 2005). The PRECEDE-PROCEED model was originally developed by Green and Kreuter in 1974 and then revised in 2005. This model is community-oriented and requires the smoker's participation in all phases to create community promotion interventions aimed at quitting smoking. The smoker's perspective, the health problem, its causes, and the smoker's behavior, as they interact with their environment, are analyzed, and interventions are adapted to fit (Green & Kreuter, 2005).

Figure 1. PRECEDE-PROCEED model. Adapted from *Precede-proceed. Health program planning: An educational and ecological approach* 4th edition, by L.W. Green & M.W. Kreuter, 2005, New York: McGraw-Hill.

This model provided a structure to support the planning of a peer-led tobacco cessation support group within an underserved community. Green and Kreuter (2005) highlight that PRECEDE ensures the program will start with the desired outcome. It

includes social, epidemiological, and ecological assessment and proceeds towards implementing interventions based on prior evaluation. PRECEDE ensures that the program is appropriate to target the health problem, whereas PROCEED starts with implementation and continues with evaluation. PROCEED includes evaluation of the process, the impact, and the outcome. PROCEED ensures the program achieves its aim. The acronym PRECEDE stands for predisposing, reinforcing, and enabling constructs in educational diagnosis and evaluation and consists of four phases (Green & Kreuter, 2005). The model includes participants and encourages ownership of the program for those it serves (Green & Kreuter, 2005). The smoker's individual, social, environmental, behavioral, and cultural factors, which contribute to the smoking, are explored. By studying the individual attributes that contribute to smoking and the obstacles to quitting, interventions aimed at helping the smoker to quit are adapted and personalized to the smoker's needs and circumstances (Green & Kreuter, 2005).

The PROCEED portion has five phases, administrative and policy diagnosis, implementation, and process, impact, and outcome evaluations. Here, the interventions developed in the PRECEDE portion are implemented, and their effectiveness is evaluated (Green & Kreuter, 2005).

Phase One: Social Diagnosis

In phase one of PRECEDE, an assessment was conducted to identify the stage of change and assess motivation to quit smoking. Readiness to change can impact smoking cessation success (Foster, Khalil, Farris, Barnighausen, & Prokhorov, 2015). The unique social components related to the health problem were identified and analyzed (Green & Kreuter, 2005). The health-related goal, as identified by the smokers to help, were

compared, evaluated, and verified through literature review. Through focused group sessions, peer mentors invited participants to identify their desired results. The participants' perception of behaviors, environmental factors, social issues, and health determinants related to smoking were explored through discussion.

Phase Two: Epidemiological Diagnosis

Quality of life was assessed by both self-report and an appropriate validated measure, during peer-led groups. Once quality of life was assessed, an epidemiological investigation was conducted. During the epidemiological phase, the issues that impede quality of life and influence the outcome the smoker seeks were identified and given top priority for change (Green & Kreuter, 2005). Peer mentors used motivational interviewing techniques for current smokers who were not ready to change (Foster et al., 2015). Motivational interviewing techniques have been found to help smokers progress through the stages of change (Cheng et al., 2014).

Phase Three: Behavioral/Environmental Diagnoses

Behavioral and environmental determinants impacting the achievement of goals identified by the smoker were recognized through literature review and smoking cessation group sessions. Through group discussions, peer mentors and participants reviewed the changeability of behavioral and environmental factors that promote cessation. The issues impacting successful cessation that were changeable were selected for behavioral modification (Green & Kreuter, 2005).

Phase Four: Educational/Organizational Diagnosis

In phase four, the predisposing, enabling, and reinforcing factors that will impede change were identified (see Figure 2). Green and Kreuter (2005) identified three factors

contributing to health-related behaviors, predisposing, enabling, and reinforcing factors. Predisposing factors are the antecedents to behavior that provide motivation to engage in the behavior (Green & Kreuter, 2005). Examples given are knowledge, attitudes, belief and values. Enabling factors are those behaviors that smokers are aware of and help to perpetuate their addiction (Green & Kreuter, 2005). Resources, barriers, and personal skills are examples of enabling factors. Reinforcing factors provide reward, incentive, or punishment and contribute to either persistence or elimination of continued behavior (Green & Kreuter, 2005).

Phase Five: Administration Policy Assessment

Step five was the investigation of organizational factors within the program that can affect the success of the interventions. Without assessing limitations of the program there was a possibility of failure related to improper support (Green & Kreuter, 2005). By identifying limitations, the practitioner can take steps to compensate for them. The resources available determined what could be implemented (Green & Kreuter, 2005).

Phase Six: Implementation

Once the program priorities were identified, the next step was to proceed to phase six, which was the development and implementation of the program. During this phase, the interventions were carried out.

Phase Seven through Nine: Process/Impact and Outcome Evaluation

In phase seven through nine of the PRECEDE-PROCEED model, the process and outcome of interventions were assessed. During phase seven the process was evaluated to determine if it was going according to plan and whether adjustments were needed. The

program activities and resources, participant health outcomes and the social benefits were assessed (Green & Kreuter, 2005).

Figure 2. Factors that influence smoking related health behaviors.

During phase eight, the goal was to determine if the use of a peer-led coach decreased cigarette usage and increased smoking cessation. There was a reassessment to see if smokers that were previously not ready to change are progressing through the stages of change. The impact of the intervention on behavioral, lifestyle, and environmental factors were evaluated in phase eight and adjustments were made accordingly.

During phase nine, the participant's desired outcome was evaluated (Green & Kreuter, 2005). An assessment was conducted to determine if the effects of the interventions are producing the outcome the community participants desired. The question was asked, were the goals those that participants desired achieved?

For this project, the PRECEDE-PROCEED model was a good fit. Smokers often fail at quit attempts and have high rates of relapse. This model allowed us the ability to include the smoker in the design and help smokers have ownership of goals. PRECEDE-PROCEED allowed us to identify factors that impede achieving the participants' desired outcome and plan interventions accordingly (Bautista-Rentero, Moret-Tatay, & Zanon-Viguer, 2013).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The purpose of this project was to develop, implement, and evaluate the effectiveness of a peer-led Smoking Cessation Support Group (SCSG) within the community of Lynwood. The Project Author (PA) conducted a comprehensive literature review to identify the foundations of establishing an SCSG and investigate factors which motivate smokers to quit and examine barriers to smoking cessation. In addition to current evidence-based practices, the review examined the role of social support in smoking cessation. This project took place within an underserved community at a local church. Thus, the literature review included studies which involved face-to-face social support in relation to smoking cessation within disadvantaged populations.

Several electronic databases were searched, including CINAHL, PubMed, Cochrane Library, and Web of Science. The search was limited to peer-reviewed academic journals written in English, published between 2013 and 2020. Inclusion criteria were studies focused on peer-led support groups, social support, and behavioral interventions related to smoking cessation. The key term searched were smoking cessation along with the Boolean phrase “and” added to the terms peer mentors, social support, combination strategies, behavioral techniques, and support groups (see Table 1). Historical perspectives, case studies, editorials, and gray literature were excluded from the literature review. Articles were excluded based on duplicates and relevance to the topic. Articles focusing on technology, social media, e-cigarettes, and pharmacological therapy alone were excluded. The electronic search yielded 523 articles. Articles were reviewed by titles and abstracts, yielding 21 articles to be included in the review (Appendix A).

Table 1

Initial Search Strategy

Topic	Search Terms	Search Term Combinations
Smoking Cessation	Support group(s)	Smoking cessation or quitting smoking and support group(s),
	Peer mentors	Peer mentors or PC and smoking cessation or quitting smoking
	Quit strategies	Smoking cessation or quitting smoking and quit strategies
	Social Support	Smoking cessation or quit smoking and social support
Community	Smoking Cessation	Community or community health and smoking cessation or quitting smoking
	Support groups	Community support groups AND smoking cessation or quit smoking
	Quit Strategies	Community smoking cessation and quit strategies
	Peer Mentors	Community peer mentors or PC and smoking cessation or quit smoking
	Social Support	Community social support and smoking cessation
Combines Treatment Approaches	Smoking Cessation	Combined treatment and smoking cessation or quitting smoking

Literature Appraisal

The studies appraised for this literature review included vulnerable populations, as this population will be the target for the project. The project will take place in a community that primarily consists of racial minorities of lower socioeconomic status and are identified as vulnerable. Disadvantaged groups experience more significant smoking-related health inequalities, which account for one-third of the differences found between ethnic groups in life expectancy (Gregoraci et al., 2017). Quantitative studies included disadvantaged groups, specifically socioeconomically disadvantaged adults (Bandiera et al., 2015; Barcelona de Mendoza & Damio, 2018), homeless (Chen, Nguyen, Malesker, & Morrow, 2016; Neisler et al., 2018), prison inmates (Bock et al., 2013), low-income African Americans (Hooper, Baker, & McNutt, 2013), Spanish-speaking smokers (Pineiro et al., 2016), and cancer survivors (Poghosyan, Darwish, Kim, & Cooley, 2016).

Qualitative studies with vulnerable populations included participants with mental illness (Dickerson et al., 2016), and socioeconomically disadvantaged participants (O’Keefe et al., 2018). Systematic reviews also included disadvantaged populations (Ford, Clifford, Gussy, & Gartner, 2013; Mitchell, Kneipp, & Giscombe, 2016). Thus, all studies reviewed contained the components that will be included in the project.

Most studies took place within the U.S. (Bandiera, Anteneh, & Guydish, 2015; Bock et al., 2013; Barcelona de Mendoza & Damio, 2018; Creswell, Cheng, & Levine, 2015; Dickerson et al., 2016; Hooper et al., 2013; Neisler et al., 2018; Mitchell et al., 2016; O’Keefe et al., 2018; Poghosyan et al., 2016). Two studies took place in Sweden (Ochsner et al., 2014; Scholz et al., 2016), one was conducted in the Netherlands (Meijer, Gebhardt, Van Lar, Kawous, & Beijik, 2016), another in Australia (Ford et al., 2013), and lastly one in Poland (Buczokowski, Marcinowicz, Czachowski, & Piszczek, 2014). These are all developed countries with established methods of treating smoking cessation, making the information garnered from the studies applicable to the present project.

Sample sizes varied from small to large (O’Keefe et al., 2018; Poghosyan et al., 2016). Larger sample sizes provided more information, reduced uncertainty, and allowed for greater ability to detect differences (Littler, 2015). Smaller sample sizes increased the possibility that the sample is unrepresentative of the population and can undermine the study’s internal and external validity (Faber & Fonseca, 2014). Most studies included both men and women of different races and ethnicities.

Data collection in the studies incorporated in this literature review varied and included in-person, online (Meijer et al. 2016; Neisler et al., 2018; Ochsner et al., 2014; Scholz et al. 2016), and over the telephone (Bandiera et al., 2015; Hooper et al., 2013;

Poghosyan et al, 2016; Scholz et al., 2016). Data collection was conducted through in-depth interviews (Bock et al. 2013; Dickerson et al., 2016), focused groups (Barcelona de Mendoza & Damio, 2018; Buczkowski et al., 2014), self-report questionnaires (Armitage, 2016; Bandiera et al., 2015; Bock et al., 2013; Chen et al., 2016; Horton & Loukas, 2013, Meijer et al., 2016; Neisler et al., 2018; Oschner et al., 2014; Poghosyan et al., 2016; Scholz et al. 2016; Yalcin, Unal, Pirdal, & Karahan, 2014), and biochemical measures (Bandiera et al., 2015; Bock et al., 2013; Creswell et al., 2015; Oschner et al., 2014; Pineiro et al. 2016; Yalcin et al., 2014). The studies included demographic information collected through in-person questionnaires or electronically through surveys. Perceived social support, stress levels, nicotine dependence, depression, coping, affect, and smoking cessation outcomes were measured.

Accurately measuring smoking cessation outcomes is an important part of assessing the efficacy of cessation strategies (WHO, 2003). Two different methods exist for measuring smoking cessation outcomes: self-report and biochemical measures, such as urine cotinine and carbon monoxide (Cheung et al., 2017). Self-report was used in assessing quit rates (Armitage, 2016; Barcelona de Mendoza & Damio, 2018; Horton & Loukas, 2013; Ochsner et al., 2014; Yalcin et al., 2014) and social support (Bandiera et al., 2015; Dickerson et al., 2016; Ochsner et al., 2014). Although self-report was widely used to measure quit rates, expired air carbon monoxide (Bandiera et al., 2015; Creswell et al., 2015; Ochsner et al., 2014) and urine cotinine levels were biochemically verified in some studies (Bock et al., 2013).

Biochemical monitoring of CO levels is an effective method of assessing current smoking status (Meredith, 2014). However, smoking cessation experts agree biochemical

measures are not always needed (Cheung et al., 2017) since evidence indicates self-reported measures of the number of cigarettes smoked correlate highly with measured biochemical levels (Velicer, Prochaska, Rossi, & Snow, 1992; Wong, Shields, Leatherdale, Malaisson, & Hammond, 2012). In the studies reviewed, social support was measured using the Interpersonal Support Evaluation [ISEL] tool (Bandiera et al., 2016; Bock et al., 2013; Creswell et al., 2015; Neisler et al., 2018) and the Social Support for Quitting Smoking Questionnaire [SSQ] (Bock et al., 2013).

The ISEL is a 12-item self-report measure of perceived social support (Bandiera et al., 2015). It measures perceived social support in four areas, including tangible help, belonging, self-esteem, and appraisal support (Bandiera et al., 2015). A higher level of nicotine dependence was associated with greater difficulty in quitting (National Institute Drug Abuse [NIDA], 2018). Measures to assess nicotine dependence included the Fagerstrom Test for Nicotine Dependence [FTND] (Bock et al., 2013; Creswell et al., 2015; Hooper et al., 2013; Yalcin et al., 2014), a shorter version of the FTND entitled the Heaviness of Smoking Index [HSI] (Neisler et al., 2018), and The Visual Analogue Scale (Creswell et al., 2015) were also used. The FTND is a reliable method to measure nicotine dependence (Svicher, Cosci, Giannini, Pistelli, & Fagerström, 2018).

The Revised Tolerance Questionnaire, based on the FTND, was also used to assess dependence on nicotine (Armitage, 2016). The FTND was the most widely used tool for measuring nicotine dependence (Svicher et al., 2018), and based on the number of cigarettes smoked and time length between cigarettes smoked (Svicher et al., 2018), and yields a score of zero (low dependency) to ten (high dependency). Stress levels, depression, coping mechanisms, affect, and motivation was inconsistently measured

among the studies appraised. The individual smoker experience of stress was measured using self-report surveys (Chen et al., 2016; Poghosyan et al., 2016), and the Ecological Momentary Assessment [EMA] response rates (Bandiera et al., 2015). Motivation to quit smoking was assessed using the motivation rating scale (Bock et al., 2013) and self-report (Buczowski et al., 2014). Coping was measured using the Brief-COPE Scale (Hooper et al., 2013; Horton & Loukas, 2013). Depression was measured in one study using the Center for Epidemiological Studies Depression Scale [CES-D], and another used Beck's Depression Inventory (Creswell et al., 2015). Affect was measured using the Positive and Negative Affect Schedule [PANA] (Hooper et al., 2013).

Overview

Tobacco use is the leading cause of death in the U.S., with 480,000 people dying annually (CDC, 2019). Almost 40 million adults and 4.7 million middle and high school students continue to smoke (CDC, 2019). Smoking prevalence is higher among disadvantaged and vulnerable populations (CDC, 2018). These populations include ethnic minorities, the underinsured, elderly, or homeless as well as those with mental illness, substance abuse, lower socioeconomic status, lower education levels, and individuals with other chronic health conditions (Maddox, 2018). Disadvantaged groups engage in higher rates of smoking compared to the general population, and their life expectancy is five years less than never smokers (CDC, 2019).

Quitting smoking as early as possible increases the smoker's life expectancy and decreases the risk of death (Jha et al., 2013). According to the CDC (2017), current smokers are individuals who have smoked more than 100 cigarettes in their lifetime and have smoked within the last 28 days (CDC, 2017). There are a variety of ways smokers

have successfully quit, including cold turkey, self-help (e.g., written materials), counseling, pharmacological management, and behavioral and social support. Behavioral support (such as brief advice and counseling) and pharmacological therapy (e.g., varenicline, bupropion, and nicotine replacement therapy) are effective evidence-based methods of helping smokers to quit (Stead et al., 2016). When these therapies are combined, there is an increased chance that the smoker will be successful in quitting (Stead et al., 2016).

Self-help refers to printed materials used to support smokers during quit attempts. Self-help does not include therapy involving health professionals, counselors, or group support (Brandon et al., 2016). Social support is defined as the types of help one receives from others and may include emotional, instrumental, informational (advice), and appraisal support (Glanz & Swartz, 2008). Counseling and medication have shown to improve smoker's chances of quitting; however, the use of these evidence-based strategies has decreased among men, young adults, uninsured individuals, minorities, and those without smoking cessation comorbidities (Tibuakuu et al., 2019). Limited use of evidence-based smoking cessation strategies may contribute to higher smoking rates for individuals in these populations (Tibuakuu et al., 2019). Although two-thirds of smokers want to quit, less than one in ten has successfully done so within the last year (CDC, 2017). Relapse among individuals who quit smoking is high, and stress within the social environment only serves to hinder their efforts to quit (Buczowski et al., 2014). In an effort to buffer the effects of stress on individuals attempting to quit, programs include social support as a component (O'Keefe et al., 2018). Social support can take place in the

clinic and community setting. Smokers prefer social support provided within their communities (O'Keefe et al., 2018).

Smoking Cessation Barriers and Motivations

For those individuals that want to quit, there can be barriers preventing successful smoking cessation. In a systematic review including 65 studies of vulnerable populations, Twyman, Bonevski, Paul, & Bryant, (2014) identified several barriers to successful smoking cessation. These included stress management, motivation, lack of support, and a high prevalence of smoking within disadvantaged communities. Motivation to quit smoking plays a key role in smoking cessation and can impact an individual's ability to quit smoking (Buczowski et al., 2014; Chen et al., 2016; Twyman et al., 2014; Scholz et al., 2016). Motivation can predict short- and long-term smoking cessation success (Pineiro et al., 2016; Scholz et al., 2016). Improved smoking quit rates are seen when smokers have a higher motivation to quit (Pineiro et al., 2016). For smokers who lack the motivation to quit, motivational interviewing [MI] was found to help with progressing through the stages of behavioral change (Cheng et al., 2014).

Motivational interviewing is a collaborative process used to help patients explore their motivation for change centered on listening, reiterating concerns, and guiding decision-making, while valuing the smoker's autonomy to quit (Cheng et al., 2014). The living environment of smokers can impact their motivation to quit, especially when there are other smokers present (Bock et al., 2013; Buczowski et al., 2014; Chen et al., 2016; Twyman et al., 2014). An environment in which smoking is banned will increase motivation to quit smoking (Buczowski et al., 2014). Quitting smoking can cause a

change in the social group for the smoker through the loss of a peer who shared the same interest of smoking (Bock et al., 2013; Mitchell et al., 2016).

Stress was frequently cited as a barrier to quitting smoking and a reason for relapse. Chen et al., (2016) found that even with 51% of smokers wanting to quit, the experience of stress in their lives, and the use of cigarettes to alleviate it, was a perceived barrier to smoking cessation. Researchers found withdrawal symptoms, such as cravings, were obstacles to smoking cessation. In addition, the lack of resources for smoking cessation was also identified as a perceived barrier (Chen et al., 2016). Research findings revealed stress was perceived as a more significant barrier to quitting than the lack of access to smoking cessation resources (Chen et al., 2016).

Smoking is used as a coping mechanism among smokers (Twyman et al., 2014). Learning healthy coping skills to equip smokers to handle stress improves quit rates (Yalcin et al., 2014). Quitting smoking itself can increase stress levels (Yalcin et al., 2014). Yalcin et al., (2014) randomized 350 smokers to a study group, and 350 smokers to a control group. Both groups received a standard quit program, including medication and behavioral counseling. The study group received five additional 90-minute sessions to teach smokers coping mechanisms and anger management strategies. The study group had higher quit rates than the control group. Teaching smokers coping mechanisms during a quit attempt can facilitate quitting (Yalcin et al., 2014). Researchers have examined the role of religion as a coping mechanism. Positive religious coping is described as finding a spiritual connection and seeking support from a divine being (Horton & Loukas, 2013). Researchers found positive religious coping decreased the likelihood of cigarette usage among female smokers (Horton & Loukas, 2013).

Smokers who quit smoking, identify the need to alleviate stress with a cigarette as the most common reason for relapse (Buczowski et al., 2014). Smokers with limited social support may benefit from social support designed to help manage stress during a quit attempt (Bandiera et al., 2015). Smoking is considered a habit, and the routine of smoking is a learned behavior (Roberts, Kerr, & Smith, 2013). Habits are behavioral patterns acquired through frequent repetition (Merriam-Webster, 2019). Implementation plans can overcome the effects of habits by identifying triggers that lead to smoking, and the development of plans that cause an individual to focus on “if-then” or “what-then” when they encounter situations they link with smoking (Armitage, 2016). For example, “if” the smoker usually smokes while drinking their morning coffee, “then” the plan is to take a walk instead of smoking. Implementation plans are designed to avert automatic responses to smoking and provide the smoker an opportunity to think through their desired responses (Armitage, 2016).

Combined Treatment Approaches

Combining treatment approaches such as behavioral support, and medication can increase a smoker’s success of quitting, by 70 to 100% (Stead et al., 2016). However, access to evidence-based smoking cessation strategies such as behavioral support and pharmacotherapy may be limited for smokers in lower socioeconomic groups (Twyman et al., 2014). Disparity was identified, with lower socioeconomic smokers being less likely to receive advice from health care providers to quit smoking than smokers with higher socioeconomic status (Browning, Ferketich, & Salsberry, 2008). A systemic review using 66 RCTs showed that adding behavioral support through group therapy along with pharmacological therapy is superior to less intense methods of promoting

smoking cessation (Stead, Carroll, & Lancaster, 2017). Behavioral support is a tailored approach to smoking cessation which may include education, advice, in person or telephone counseling (Stead et al., 2016).

Social Support Impact on Smoking Cessation

The literature identified the benefits of social support and its impact on smoking cessation. Meijer et al., (2016) established participants who intended to quit smoking expected and desired social support during quit attempts. Social support is positively correlated with motivation, confidence, and intentions to quit smoking (Bock et al., 2013). The addition of social support to pharmacological therapy and behavioral techniques, has been shown to decrease cigarette usage among smokers (Bandiera et al., 2015; Barcelona de Mendoza & Damio, 2018; Creswell et al., 2015; Dickerson et al., 2016; Neisler et al., 2018; Poghosyan et al., 2016; Scholz et al. 2016; Stead et al., 2017) and increase the probability of maintaining long term cessation. Social support provides a buffer against the harmful effects of nicotine withdrawal and is associated with a longer stretch of cessation to relapse (Creswell et al., 2015). Social support was also found to improve smoking cessation success through decreasing stress during quit attempts (Bandiera et al., 2015). A meta-analysis of 53 smoking cessation RCTs that included combined treatment approaches with medication, behavioral and social support using group support was more effective than self-help or other less intensive strategies alone (Stead et al., 2016). In a study conducted using 8,055 cancer survivors, those with limited social support and mental distress were more likely to be current smokers (Poghosyan et al., 2016). Research indicates social support plays a role in helping cancer patients cope with distress (Poghosyan et al., 2016).

Three studies examined the effectiveness of utilizing PCs, medication and behavioral interventions to increase quit rates among smokers (Barcelona de Mendoza & Damio, 2018; Dickerson et al., 2016; Ford et al., 2013). A statistically significant increase in quitting smoking was seen when PCs were added as an intervention to other evidence-based strategies in both clinic and the community setting (Barcelona de Mendoza & Damio, 2018). In another study, peer mentor relationships were established with 30 adult smokers with mental illness during 24 group sessions. Peer mentors modeled non-smoking behavior throughout group sessions, provided smoking cessation education, motivation enhancement, skills training, and goal-setting activities (Dickerson et al., 2016). Sessions were one hour in length and given over a six-month period. Nicotine replacement was offered as a pharmacological component to smokers who were interested. The number of cigarettes smoked was assessed at baseline and again measured at three months and six months. Researchers concluded participants in the experimental group smoked significantly fewer cigarettes compared to the control group (Dickerson et al., 2016).

Ford et al. (2013) conducted a systematic review of eight studies with peer support interventions added to pharmacological therapy and behavioral strategies. Evidence supports there are more positive benefits when peer support programs are added to other evidence-based strategies among disadvantaged populations compared to non-disadvantage populations (Ford et al., 2013). Smokers desired other non-smoking types of support from peer mentors (Dickerson et al., 2016). This appears to be related to the connection which took place when smokers connected with peer mentors (Ford et al., 2013).

The qualitative studies reviewed explored the experiences and perspectives of peer mentors and participants who attempted to quit smoking and the impact of peer support on cigarette use and quit rates. There was an increase in quit rates when participants felt supported by a mentor (Burns, Rothman, Fu, Lindgren, & Joseph, 2013). The results support the benefits of social support along with pharmacological therapy and behavioral strategies for decreasing cigarette usage and increasing quit rates (Bandiera et al., 2016; Barcelona de Mendoza & Damio, 2018; Creswell et al., 2015; Dickerson et al., 2016; Scholz et al., 2016; Neisler et al., 2018; Stead et al., 2017; Poghosyan et al., 2016).

Limitations

The studies reviewed had some limitations. Most of the studies used self-report to measure smoking cessation outcomes (Armitage, 2016; Barcelona de Mendoza & Damio, 2018; Horton & Loukas, 2013; Ochsner et al., 2014; Yalcin et al., 2014) and only four used biochemical validation (Bandiera et al., 2015; Bock et al., 2013; Creswell et al., 2015; Ochsner et al., 2014). Experts conclude self-report and biochemical validation, either through cotinine levels or expired carbon monoxide, are acceptable methods for measuring smoking cessation outcomes (Cheung et al., 2017). However, it is difficult to compare self-report information with objective data since there is the possibility of self-report bias, which may impact the validity of the studies (Kim et al., 2013).

Several of the studies used small sample sizes indicating there may have been challenges such as cost, recruitment, and attrition issues affecting the studies population (Armitage, 2016; Bandiera et al., 2015; Barcelona de Mendoza & Damio, 2018; Buczkowski et al., 2014; Chen et al., 2016; Dickerson et al., 2016; Hooper et al., 2013; O'Keefe et al., 2018; Ochsner et al., 2014; Scholz et al., 2016). The research concluded

fewer cigarettes were smoked when peer-led coaches were combined with other evidence-based strategies. However, programs utilizing peer mentors were of short duration with limited follow-up to assess cessation outcomes. The studies follow up ranged from three (Barcelona de Mendoza & Damio, 2018) to six months post-program (Dickerson et al., 2016). The preferred time frame for follow-up smoking cessation outcomes based on best practices is six and twelve months (Cheung et al., 2017). Short program durations of six months or less is a limited time-frame to develop trust between PCs and smokers. Although factors other than time can affect trust in peer relationships, a recent meta-analysis indicated the length of time in relationships is positively correlated with trust (Vanneste, Puranam, & Kretschmer, 2013). Disadvantaged populations report lower levels of trust in their health care providers and higher levels of trust associated with treatment adherence (Abel & Eford, 2018). There is a need for studies including longer duration of peer mentor programs to promote smoking cessation. Studies within the community were desired for this project; although community-based work can be disorganized and lack control (O'Keefe et al., 2018), the benefits outweighed the lack of control for the purpose of this community-based project.

The research reviewed concludes social support does influence smoking-related behaviors, although there was no consensus on the mechanisms involved. The stress-buffering theory and the direct effects model were cited in the literature as possible mechanisms explaining how social support decreases smoking-related behaviors. The stress-buffering theory concludes social support buffers stress during quit attempts, and the direct effect model concludes social support has an overall benefit on participant's health and wellbeing (Poghosyan et al., 2016). Convenience sampling was a limitation in

four of the studies (Barcelona de Mendoza & Damio, 2018; Creswell et al., 2015; Pineiro et al., 2016; Scholz et al., 2016). These participants were recruited as part of larger trials of smoking cessation, and the participants may have had higher levels of motivation to seek treatment to quit. Convenience sampling is less generalizable to the general population than probability; however, probability samples can be cost prohibitive (Jager, Putnick, & Bornstein, 2017).

Future studies should measure motivation levels and include both motivated and non-motivated participants to results are reproducible across these groups. None of the studies examined the role of negative social support in sustaining smoking-related behaviors, indicating there is limited research in this area. Rook (1984) describes four types of negative social support: uncaring behavior; unsolicited or unreliable instruction; failure to deliver support in times of need; and rejection or negligence. Evaluating the impact of negative social support on smoking cessation is recommended for future study.

Conclusion

Despite limitations of studies appraised, sufficient evidence exists supporting the benefits of social support on smoking. This review of the literature demonstrates the benefit of adding social support to other evidence-based smoking cessation strategies. Evidence supports adding a peer component to smoking cessation programs has positive benefits on smoking in high-risk communities. Utilizing group support strategies is an effective approach to decrease cigarette usage and improve cessation rates among smokers.

Since the early 1900s, progress has been made in understanding the harmful effects of tobacco. Through research we have gained an understanding regarding the

harms of tobacco. The first cohort study exposing the negative impacts of tobacco was conducted in the 1950s, and included 188,000 participants (ACS, 2014). Despite knowing the harms of tobacco for more than 50 years, it remains the leading preventable cause of death in the U.S. (CDC, 2019). The tobacco industry continues to spend billions of dollars each year promoting their products, which outspends the costs aimed at targeting smoking cessation programs (CDC, 2019).

The tobacco industry advertises certain products disproportionately in specific minority racial and ethnic groups such as African Americans (American Lung Association, 2019). For this project, the aim is to impact smoking cessation rates within a predominantly minority high-risk community (Data USA, 2017). Group support will be combined with other evidence-based smoking cessation strategies and led by peer coaches to help smokers decrease their consumption of tobacco.

METHODS

This quality improvement project (QI) aimed to develop, implement, and evaluate the effectiveness of a peer-led group for current smokers within the community of Lynwood. The four phases of the project consisted of PC recruitment, PC training, smoker recruitment, and the SCSG. The methods section consists of the design of the project, the setting, description of the sample, ethical issues, implementation, and data collection and instruments.

Current Practices

Currently, patients who are motivated to quit smoking go to their primary care providers for help. Seventy percent of smokers see a medical provider at least once a year (Danesh, Paskett, & Ferketich, 2014). The primary care provider may prescribe medication to abolish withdrawal symptoms and refer the patient to the state-run telephone quit line 1-800-NO-BUTTS. This quit line offers over the phone counseling, nicotine replacement therapy, text messaging, self-help materials, online help, and referrals to local providers who can help with smoking cessation (California Smokers Helpline, 2019).

Design and Setting

This QI project involved the development, implementation, and evaluation of a peer-led smoking cessation support group within the community of Lynwood and training of PCs to lead the smoking cessation support group developed by this project and future support groups in the area of Lynwood. This project was designed to address the lack of available smoking cessation resources within Lynwood (Saint Francis Medical Center, 2019).

This project was conducted at a local community agency, referred to as the Immigration Center. The Immigration Center is a faith-based, nonprofit organization that assists immigrant families in becoming self-sufficient and provides low-cost immigration, legal assistance, and representation. The Immigration Center is in the city of Lynwood, at Lyn-Gate Neighborhood Church. It was selected for the project due to existing services that are related to supporting individuals in the local community. The smoking cessation project was an added service that the organization agreed to participate in (see Appendix B).

Project Author Background and Qualifications

The PA is an expert in smoking cessation and is from the local community of Lynwood. She is well known to the local church where PCs were recruited. The PA has received formal training as a Tobacco Treatment Specialist [TTS] through the Mayo Clinic. Smokers who receive cessation services from a TTS have higher quit rates (Kotz, Brown, & West, 2014). The PA has conducted over 100 tobacco treatment support groups. The PA is a native English speaker and does not speak or understand Spanish. The immigration center provided the use of an interpreter.

Sample

The participants of PCs and smokers were obtained from the population of the community of Lynwood. PCs were recruited from the church associated with the immigration center, and smokers were from the local communities in and around Lynwood. Participants were at least 18 years old, and spoke either English, Spanish, or were bilingual.

Peer Coaches

The PA recruited twenty-five PCs who met the eligibility criteria. The eligibility criteria consisted of individuals who share the same community and sociocultural status as the smoker. Participants were 18 years old with a high school diploma or the equivalent. The criteria used to select PCs were determined based upon established parameters supported by the literature and have been proven effective in selecting competent coaches (Barcelona de Mendoza & Damio, 2018; Dickerson et al., 2016). Both Spanish and English-speaking PCs were recruited.

Smokers

Smokers were recruited from the local church associated with the immigration center, local hospital(s), and community health clinic(s). Participants were at least 18 years old, current smokers, and had a desire to quit smoking. Smokers under the age of 18 and those afflicted with having concurrent drug or alcohol dependency issues were excluded from the program.

Ethical Issues

Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval was obtained from California State University, Fullerton. There was minimal risk to participants as the interventions utilized were supportive listening and education to assist smokers in their journey to quit smoking. If a smoker experienced distress due to their efforts to quit smoking, the smoker was immediately referred to a free telephone distress line, 1-800-854-7771, to speak to someone about their feelings (Department of Mental Health, LA County, 2020). No identifying demographic information was collected; participation in the project was anonymous, and the results were reported aggregate. There was minimal risk to PCs as

the services they provided were non-invasive and only involved supportive listening and education.

Data Collection

The sociodemographic data for both PCs and smokers including gender, age, ethnicity, spoken language, and smoking history (see Appendix E). Additional information was collected for the smoking group, which included the number of cigarettes smoked before participation in the support group and after participation. The dependent variables were the number of cigarettes smoked, readiness for change, and perceived social support at baseline, and after participation in the SCSG.

Evaluation Checklist

The project consisted of 16 PCs who educated and supported smokers during the four-week SCSG. During the seventh and eighth training modules, PCs facilitated a mock SCSG where their leadership skills were assessed by the PA with an evaluation checklist (see Appendix F). The evaluation checklist was used to observe peer coaches' behaviors during the mock SCSG to evaluate whether they used supportive, evidence-based interventions learned during the training. The checklist utilized patient-centered communication and MI interviewing techniques. Patient-centered communication was demonstrated by responding to participants' feelings, preferences and needs (Hashim, 2017).

Using patient-centered communication allows for open discussion between participants and those seeking to improve their health (Hashim, 2017). The evaluation checklist determined the presence or absence of the desired group leadership skills. During the mock SCSG, the PCs needed to engage in inclusive behaviors such as

including all participants in the discussions, using verbal transitions between participants, encouraging uninterrupted conversations, and redirecting sidebar conversations. The PCs ability to establish rapport with participants was determined if they sustained eye contact and body language with legs and arms uncrossed and leaning slightly forward (Hashim, 2017). Empathy was demonstrated by the PCs being able to reflect the participant's thoughts and feelings.

The checklist also evaluated the MI skills including reflective listening, asking open ended questions, summarizing conversations, and affirming participants (Osterlund Efrainsson, 2012). A second mock support group with PCs was conducted to reinforce the training during the eighth module.

After completion of the SCSG, the PCs were individually interviewed on the phone to discuss their experiences and provide feedback regarding their education and training. The PCs were asked the following open-ended questions: "What was it like for you to be a PC?," "Did you feel you were helpful as a PC?," "What challenges did you face as a PC?," and "Did the training help you with any addiction tendencies you struggle with?"

Smoking History Questions

Smoking history of the smokers was assessed during the first and last SCSG through self-report by answering the following questions: "how many cigarettes are you smoking daily?" and "are you currently a smoking cigarette?" (see Appendix E). The use of self-report is considered a reliable method for assessing the number of cigarettes smoked, since it correlates highly with measured carbon monoxide and/or cotinine levels

(Soulakova, Hartman, Liu, Willis, & Augustine, 2012; Velicer et al., 1992, Wong et al., 2012; Cheung et al., 2017).

Readiness Ruler

The PCs measured the smokers' readiness for change during the first SCSG utilizing the Readiness Ruler (RR) (see Appendix C). The RR was developed by Miller and Rollnick; it offers a continuum from "not prepared to change" to the "ready to change" on a 10-point scale (Miller & Rollnick, 2002). The RR was selected since it is easy to use and capable of determining a person's baseline readiness for predicted behavior change (Boudreaux, 2012).

Although recommended for use in clinical practice, there is limited research on the RR (Hesse, 2006).

Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support

Social support perceived by smokers was measured at baseline and at the end of the SCSG using the Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (MSPSS) (see Appendix G). The MSPSS was developed by Zimet, Dahlem, Zimet, and Farley (1988) as a brief self-reported measure of perceived social support. The MSPSS is a 12-item Likert scale survey. The items of the instrument are divided into three sources of support from family, friends, and/or significant others; each source included four questions about support (Zimet et al., 1988). Each item was rated on a seven-point scale from strongly disagree, rated 1, to strongly agree, rated 7. Total scores of the items range from one to seven with 1 to 2.9 indicating low, 3 to 5 indicating medium, and 6 and 7 indicating high levels of perceived social support.

The MSPSS was easy to administer and was used due to its ability to measure the three sources of social support, which helped to describe support systems identified in the literature. Additionally, the MSPSS is a well-tested survey that has good internal reliability with a Cronbach's coefficient Alpha of .88 and adequate stability over time with a test-test reliability of .85. It has moderate construct validity with a score of $-.25$, $<.01$ (Zimet et al., 1988).

Implementation

The implementation phase began once IRB approval was obtained. The church affiliated with the Immigration Center was the facility used to recruit PCs. Therefore, the permission of the parishioner in-charge was sought and granted. The parishioners of the church were educated about the project, its benefits to the community, and purposes. This section discussed the various phases of conducting this QI project (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Project phases.

Phase One: Recruitment

The first phase emphasized the role of peers as coaches and involved the recruitment of the PCs. A sign-up sheet was offered for individuals interested and volunteered to participate. Initially, twenty-five individuals signed up and were contacted by the PA. During the initial contact, the volunteers were screened using the predetermined eligibility criteria for this project. All of the volunteers met eligibility and therefore were invited to become PCs. They were sent a text message notifying them of the date and time of the first training session. A follow up message was sent to all the volunteers who had not responded to the first message. As a result, all of the twenty-five volunteers attended the first PC module.

Phase Two: Training of Peer Coaches

The second phase of the project involved training the 25 volunteers to become PCs. The training consisted of eight 90-minute educational modules given weekly (see Table 2). The educational modules involved the following teaching strategies: PowerPoint presentations, reflective exercises, role plays, and mock support groups. The education was written to a fifth-grade reading level and without jargon.

The first module addressed the harms of cigarette smoking, nicotine addiction and an overview of the medications used to prevent nicotine withdrawal symptoms. Reflective exercises were integrated into modules one and two. Peer Coaches were encouraged to reflect on their own experiences with addiction and the antecedents to their addictive behaviors. Reflections were designed to enhance peer coaches' learning experiences and increase their ability to identify with the smokers. Reflection has been shown to enhance the learning experiences (Larsen, London, & Make, 2016). The second

module involved. During module two, PCs were asked to reflect on their past experiences at trying to change an addictive behavior and their feelings after relapse which can assist PCs in relating to the smokers. The use of tobacco control efforts have de-normalized smoking that makes smoking appear to be negative and increases stigma, which may impact the ability of PCs to identify with smokers and deliver effective support (Bell, Salmon, Bowers, Bell, & McCullough, 2010).

The third module emphasized smoking history, medication management, and community referrals. Peer coaches were given a list of local community resources to refer smokers who expressed a desire for smoking cessation medication. The fourth module entailed information regarding stages of change, assessing readiness for change and MI techniques, such as reflective listening, affirmations, summaries, and asking open-ended questions such as “what are your concerns about quitting smoking.” The fifth module discussed social support and how to assess it using the MSPSS; it also conferred various ways to increase support such as “asking a PC to check in with you once or twice a week.” The sixth module pertained to facilitating a SCSG and regular check ins via text messages. Finally, the seventh and eight modules provided an experiential component in which the PCs conducted and practiced mock support groups. During the mock support groups, the PCs practiced the skills taught in the previous modules. They were observed and evaluated through feedback which helped them to improve their skills.

For those PCs who were Spanish speaking, the Immigration Center provided Spanish interpreters. Peer coaches needing interpretation were provided a headset in which they could listen to the translation during the eight weeks of training.

Phase Three: Recruitment of Smokers

Phase three consisted of recruitment of smokers from the local community. Flyers advertising the program were distributed at the local hospital, clinics, and the church (see Appendix H). The PA discussed the project with local medical providers, who had specialties in pulmonology, internal medicine, vascular surgery, and wound care, so they can refer smokers to the SCSG. Flyers were left with the medical providers after the meetings. The flyers contained a brief description of the project and its purposes in addition to the contact information for the PA. Most of the medical providers agreed to refer smokers using the flyer. Once volunteer smokers contacted the PA, their questions were answered and they were screened at the end of the discussion about the project. Eligible smokers were given information regarding dates and times of the support groups.

Phase Four: Conducting the Smoking Cessation Support Group

The twelve-week SCSG led by PCs was conducted at the Immigration Center during phase four of the project. Peer Coaches used evidence-based strategies taught during the eight-weeks of training to help smokers quit. They obtained the smoker's history, assessed smokers' readiness for change using the RR, and measured social support using the MSPSS.

If the smoker expressed a desire for smoking cessation medication, PCs provided a referral to 1-800-No-Butts or a local community clinic (see Appendix D). During the SCSG, PCs, as role models, shared relevant personal experiences with smokers and were paired with them based on shared language. The PCs and smokers contacted each other at least twice a week via text messages to maintain connections in between the SCSG sessions. Research indicated that the use of text messages is an effective tool for

increasing smoking cessation quit rates when combined with other evidence-based strategies (Naughton et al. 2017).

Table 2

Training Topics

Module Number	Description
Module 1	Harms of Cigarette Smoking Nicotine Addiction Withdrawal Symptoms & Relapse
Module 2	Relapse Recognizing Triggers Breaking Habit Links Coping & Mechanisms for Stress
Module 3	Taking Smoking History Medication Management Community Referrals
Module 4	Stages of Change Assessing Readiness for Change Motivational Interviewing Techniques
Module 5	Assessing Social Support How to Increase Social Support
Module 6	Support group training & text messaging
Module 7	Mock Support Group & Evaluations
Module 8	Mock Support Group & Evaluations

The methods used to conduct a peer-led SCSG in the high-risk community of Lynwood were evidence-based and specific to community health.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Sociodemographic Characteristics of Peer Coaches

Descriptive analysis was used to identify the sociodemographic characteristics of the PCs who completed the training and participated in the SCSG. Initially, 25 PCs began the eight training modules with 16 PCs completing all modules. However, when the SCSG sessions began, only 6 PCs continued to participate in the program. The majority of the PCs were Hispanic ($n = 5$, 83%), and one was Native American ($n = 1$, 17%). Five PCs spoke fluent Spanish. The average age of the PCs was 39 years old. Half of the PCs were female ($n = 3$, 50%). Two PCs were former smokers (33%), and four never smoked (67%). Table 3 provides more details about sociodemographic data of the PCs.

Table 3

Peer Coach Demographics

PC Demographics	n	Percentages
Gender		
Females	3	50%
Males	3	50%
Age (years)		
30-40	5	83%
40-60	1	17%
Race		
Hispanic	5	83%
Native America	1	17%
Language		
Bilingual	2	33%
Spanish	3	50%
English	1	17%
Smoking Status		
Never Smoker	4	67%
Former Smoker	2	33%

Evaluation of Peer Coaches

During the seventh and eighth training modules, the PCs were rated on the presence or absence of the three criteria to determine their effectiveness at facilitating a SCSG. The three criteria were the PCs opened the groups by introducing themselves, used patient-centered communication and MI techniques, and closed the sessions by recapping and providing encouraging statements, such as, “you are smoking less than before” or “you showed up for the group today.” The results showed that during the first mock support group, three of the PCs practiced effective leadership skills as they engaged in all three criteria. Since all PCs did not meet the criteria, a mock demonstration was conducted by the PA to reinforce the training. The mock demonstration included role play of desired interactions between PCs and participants. The PCs then conducted a second mock support session during which all of the six PCs were re-evaluated and met the criteria for engaging in leadership skills.

Qualitative Data about the Peer Coaching Experience

Due to a worldwide pandemic, COVID-19, the proposed focus groups could not be conducted in person due to social distancing restrictions. Instead, the PCs were interviewed individually through telephone interviews at the end of the SCSG. Interview questions included: What was it like for you to be a PC? Did you feel you were helpful as a PC? What challenges did you face as a PC? Did the training help you with any addiction tendencies you struggle with? The qualitative data collected was transcribed and coded to identify common themes. Although PCs described various experiences related to their role as PCs, four themes were identified.

The first theme was self-reflection. One PC made statements such as “first, I looked at life differently, and understood that the first change was going to be me, in order to help others with smoking” and “I felt more responsible and I tried to focus on other things when dealing with my own addiction.” Another stated “I faced coming to terms with my own issues that I was not aware of and this made me more empathetic towards participants.”

The second theme was feelings of empowerment through gaining knowledge and skills. Peer coaches’ statements included “there is a need to quit smoking and lack of knowledge in our community on this subject. I felt that I was able to let others know that there is help to quit smoking,” and “the skills I learned are adaptable to addictions other than smoking and now I can make better choices with my addiction tendencies.”

The third theme was identified as lack of time to build trust with participants. One PC said “with more time I can earn his trust,” and another mentioned “more than four weeks was needed to help them quit smoking.” Several PCs expressed their concern with the reduced time frame of the SCSG, from 12 weeks to four weeks. One PC stated “I wish we had more time” and several PCs inquired “when could we start again?”

The fourth theme reflected gratitude and satisfaction with the program. Peer coaches’ statements included “it is an honor to be part of this program” and “please let us know when this starts again, I want to continue.” They expressed being grateful for the opportunity to be part of the SCSG. PCs also appreciated the four weeks of relationship building with participants. One peer coach stated “I enjoyed getting to know them” and “this was a great experience.” Another described “I looked forward to coming to the SCSG each week.” Several PCs found connecting through text messaging with

participants outside of the SCSG to be beneficial. One PC indicated “communicating through texting reinforced our commitment beyond the group” and “reaching out to check on someone else helped me to forget what I was going through.”

Sociodemographic Characteristics of Smoker Participants

Ten smokers were recruited from the local church associated with the immigration center, local hospitals, and community health clinics. Five out of those ten referred smokers expressed an interest and were included as participants in the SCSG. Two potential participants lacked transportation, and one could not drive at night. The remaining two declined to participate.

The descriptive analysis revealed that four of the five participants in the SCSG were Black (80%) and one was Hispanic (20%). Four of the participants spoke English (80%) and one spoke Spanish only (20%). Three of the participants were women (60%). The age range of the participants was 40 to 60. One of the participants attending the SCSG was homeless (20%) (See Table 4).

Readiness of Smokers to Quit Smoking

Prior to the start of the SCSG, the readiness ruler to assess smokers' readiness to change indicated that four of the participants (80%) indicated a readiness to change by rating themselves as seven or above. The fifth participant (20%) was not ready to change and marked himself one on the ten-point scale; however, this participant was included in the SCSG since he/she expressed a desire to participate.

Table 4

Participant Demographics

PC Demographics	n	Percentages
Gender		
Females	3	60%
Males	2	40%
Age (years)		
30-40	0	0%
40-60	5	100%
Race		
Hispanic	1	20%
Black	4	80%
Language		
Bilingual	0	0%
Spanish	1	20%
English	4	80%
Homeless	1	20%
Former Smoker	2	33%

One participant disclosed they were receiving medication to quit smoking whereas the other four failed to obtain any smoking cessation medications since two of them were awaiting upcoming appointments with their providers and the other two failed to follow up and did not provide any further feedback. The participant receiving medication was able to quit smoking by the fourth week of the SCSG. Two participants were able to decrease the number of cigarettes smoked by 30 cigarettes every week by the end of the fourth week of the SCSG, whereas the other two participants maintained their current cigarette usage.

Perception of Social Support

Data analysis of the perceptions of social support of smokers before and after the SCSG showed that the majority of the smoker participants ($n = 4$, 80%) had an increase in their perceived social support scores by the fourth week attending the SCSG. At baseline, three participants self-reported levels of social support between 3 and 5, suggesting moderate levels; however, their perceived social support became above 7 on the MSPSS by the fourth week of the SCSG, indicating a higher level of social support.

One of the participants reported low perceived social support at baseline ($score = 2$), however, it became moderate at the end of the fourth week of the SCSG ($score = 4$). Only one individual did not perceive an increase in their social support and continued to indicate low perception of social support levels despite attendance in the SCSG. The fifth participant who self-identified as homeless had maintained the same scores of perceived social support at baseline and at the end of the SCSG ($score = 1$).

The SCSG was proposed to be conducted for 12 weeks; however, due to social distancing measures caused by the global pandemic, the participants were able to attend for four weeks.

DISCUSSION

Peer Coaches

This QI project was able to successfully train PCs to lead smoking cessation support groups in an underserved community. There were 25 PCs who initially began the training with six who remained and facilitated the SCSG. This high attrition of the PCs may be attributed to lack of financial incentives, limited community recognition of the program, personal time constraints due to work, and/or church or family commitments (Ngilangwa & Mgomella, 2018). Several of the PCs that quit had indicated they preferred to attend a bible study which was taking place on the same night as the SCSG. Also, there was a six-week break between the end of PC training and the start of the SCSG, due to difficulties with recruiting smokers, which may have further contributed to PC dropout. Research has suggested that disruptions in training can cause a high-risk of participant drop out (Ngugi et al., 2018). There was no PC attrition during the SCSG which could be attributed to the relationship PCs developed with participants. Research shows PCs relationships with participants strongly influences their ability to remain engaged (Maes & Kalofonos, 2013).

The PCs recruited by this project demonstrated representative sociodemographic characteristics and shared similar characteristics with the community from which they were drawn. The PCs and the participants were all people of color, thus, they shared cultural similarities. Research indicated effective smoking cessation support can be accomplished by PCs who are culturally similar to those who they support (Barcelona de Mendoza & Damio, 2018). Although the PCs did not share a similar smoking history with participants, they were able to successfully facilitate the SCSG, perhaps because the

PCs had the motivation and capacity to provide support to participants especially that they were recruited locally. Several PCs expressed a desire to have a career in the healthcare field. Research suggested that individuals who seek to become PCs are often individuals who desire to serve their community and have a career in healthcare (Ngilangwa & Mgomella, 2018).

The eight training modules imparted PCs with knowledge and skills needed to facilitate the SCSGs. During the PC interviews, several PCs reported feelings of empowerment because they were gaining knowledge and skills to enable them to help their community. The integration of a hands-on component, the mock support groups, assisted in improving PCs competencies to facilitate peer-led smoking cessation support groups. Hands-on approaches to training can be more effective than classroom learning (Freeman et al., 2014). The peer coaches were evaluated twice to achieve the goal of training them until they successfully demonstrated an ability to lead a SCSG using learned evidence-based strategies such as supportive MI techniques and patient-centered communication and other leadership skills. Additionally, using an expert to train the trainer approach has shown to be effective in improving PC adherence and competency to MI techniques (Martino et al, 2011).

The timeframe in which the PC training took place was over 12 hours during eight training modules. Evidence suggest smokers' well-being is positively reflected when cessation programs include a peer coaching component, despite varying time frames allowed for PC training. According to Barcelona de Mendoza and Damio (2018), PCs who are trained for at least 80 hours in smoking cessation techniques can improve a participant's chance of quitting smoking. However, other studies have shown that PCs

recruited from a local church and trained over ten hours in a two-day period positively impacted the health behaviors of smokers (Tang, Nwankwo, Whiten, & Oney, 2014).

This project trained PCs for 12 hours and benefits were demonstrated in the behaviors of PCs and participants in the SCSG.

Compiled qualitative data collected from the PCs in this project, despite the limited timeframe, showed that the majority of the PCs had positive self-reflections, such as feeling more responsible, and described their training as empowering and satisfying experience. They also expressed a desire to start facilitating and leading a SCSG as soon as they could, considering the COVID-19 pandemic. Additionally, PCs reported unexpected benefits from the eight training modules such as a desire to work on their own addictive behaviors prior to facilitating the SCSG. Also, a high value was placed on the knowledge gained through the training to be competent in facilitating the SCSG.

Studies of peer-led groups have identified empowerment as key to becoming an effective leader (McCreary, Kaponda, Davis, Kalengamaliro, & Norr, 2013; Mpembeni et al., 2015; Sommanustweechai et al., 2016). Peer coaches felt that the limited timeframe allowed for the project may conflict with their ability to build trust with smoker participants. In support of the literature, they emphasized that relationships with smokers helped to keep them engaged; perceived trust with the community was found to be an integral part of the role of the PCs (Holzer & Kass, 2015; Mishra, 2014). Proper implementation of a community intervention requires a trust relationship to engage community participants and to effectively implement and sustain an intervention (Holzer & Kass, 2015). A prior connection between the PA of this project and the community, through the local church, may have contributed to the willingness of the PCs to lead the

SCSG. Thus, positive prior relationships can decrease the necessary length of time to build trust and improve community engagement such as was found in the present project (Holzer & Kass, 2015).

Peer coaches expressed their gratitude and satisfaction with the training experience and believed it helped them be mentors. Research showed that PCs had higher satisfaction when they felt they had the capacity to provide services to their communities (Mpembeni et al., 2015).

Peer coaches expressed satisfaction with the training experience and believed it helped them to lead the SCSG. Research indicates confidence of PCs in providing health-related services was positively correlated with their participation in recent training (Sommanustweechai et al., 2016). Peer coaching experience may influence self-confidence, autonomy, and knowledge (Alsaleh, Alabdulhadi, & Airwaished, 2017; Plowright et al., 2018).

Participants in the Smoking Cessation Support Group

The SCSG was proposed to be conducted for twelve weeks but it was halted after the fourth week due to social distancing requirements caused by the COVID-19 pandemic and the project time constraints, which may have influenced the outcome of the SCSG (Tang et al., 2014). Social distancing restrictions, presented by the COVID-19 pandemic, were an unforeseen barrier to the completion of the SCSG. Switching the SCSG from in person to telephone or via a social media platform was not possible due to lack of technology or inability to navigate that technology by both of the PCs and smoker participants.

Despite all the efforts to recruit at least ten smokers, only five participated in the SCSG. Several barriers to recruiting smokers were identified in the literature based on participants' sociodemographic characteristics and the timeframe in which a project takes place (Kale, Gilbert, & Sutton, 2019). Lack of information and confidence in smoking cessation services was reported by smokers as one of the main reasons for not engaging in smoking cessation support services (Kale et al., 2019). For this project, lack of available resources was a barrier to recruitment since it was difficult to attract smokers who are not already in an established program. According to the literature, when providing an intervention, it is often more optimal to layer on an additional peer coaching component to an existing SCSG rather than development of a new program (Barcelona de Mendoza & Damio, 2018). Partnering with a larger cessation support group can help improve recruitment of smokers and significantly increase the rates of quitting smoking (Barcelona de Mendoza & Damio, 2018).

An additional barrier to participant recruitment in the present project was the lack of transportation and an inability to drive at night. One potential participant was over 80 and was not able to drive at night; thus, he was not able to be part of the SCSG. Other potential participants reported they were not able to arrange for transportation to the SCSGs; despite, their desire to be part of the program. Smokers in underserved areas may not view quitting smoking as a high priority considering they may have other competing needs and demands (Wijk, Landais, & Harting, 2019). A recent community assessment in Lynwood indicated that community members are not able to focus on their health needs due to more pressing financial priorities such rent and food (Saint Francis Medical Center, 2019).

The SCSG demonstrated a positive outcome since smokers reported a decrease in the number of cigarettes smoked weekly. The majority of the smoker participants smoked 100 cigarettes during the first week of the SCSG; by the fourth and final week, they smoked 70 cigarettes. Therefore, this project was able to assist smokers which may be accredited, in part, to the role of social support provided in the support group to treat such an addictive behavior; group support was found to increase smoking quit rates (Stead et al., 2017).

Smoker participants reported higher perceptions of social support at the end of the SCSG. This may be reflective of the peer-led component of the project which was found to be effective in helping smokers to decrease cigarette smoking especially in high risk areas (Barcelona de Mendoza & Damio, 2018; Dickerson et al., 2016). Peer coaches recruited from a local church and trained over ten hours in a two-day period positively impacted the health behaviors of the participants (Tang et al., 2014). The one participant that maintained the same level of cigarette usage in this project was the participant who self-identified as homeless. This participant did not report an increase in perceived social support, perhaps because he/she was not well received by the other members of the SCSG. This same participant did not express readiness on the RR. Homeless individuals experience greater subsistence difficulties and are less likely to quit smoking (Baggett et al., 2018). On the other hand, the only participant who completely quit smoking was using a smoking cessation medication to manage withdrawal symptoms. Medication is an evidence-based intervention used for smoking cessation and was correlated with higher smoking quit rates (CDC, 2017; Stead et al., 2016).

This QI project demonstrated that local community agencies, such as churches, can provide a no-cost setting to conduct SCSGs. Peer-led health programs can effectively be conducted in faith-based locations in which the participants are not members of the congregation (Tang et al., 2014). Faith-based locations can be considered as a potential source for recruitment since the members of the congregation, in this project, volunteered to serve as PCs.

Despite the great benefits of conducting an SCSG in a local community, there were unique challenges that needed to be addressed in this project. Both lack of communication and scheduling conflicts had to be resolved. Some church events were scheduled for the same time as the SCSG sessions which increased the attrition rates since some PCs dropped out to attend the church events. Additional challenges included environmental issues with the meeting room. Both of the PCs and participants complained that the room used for the SCSG sessions was too hot in addition to some other situational issues and distractions.

This project highlights the benefits and challenges experienced throughout the implementation of a peer-led SCSG in a high-risk, underserved population in Lynwood. Individuals face various difficulties when trying to quit smoking; evidence supports the use of medication, behavioral interventions, and counseling as strategies to aid in smoking cessation (Stead et al., 2016). Consistent with the literature, unique challenges were experienced when a peer-led SCSG was implemented in this QI project (Barcelona de Mendoza & Damio, 2018; Dickerson et al., 2016; Ford et al., 2013). Challenges were related to PC attrition, support from local clinics, smoker recruitment, training

environment, and difficulty overcoming unforeseen barriers such as transportation issues and a global pandemic.

Benefits of this project included effective training of PCs to lead smoking cessation support groups, a decrease in the number of smoked cigarettes, and reported higher levels of perceived social support after attending the SCSG. The PCs also reported positive experiences such as helping them understand their own addictive behaviors and feeling empowered with more knowledge and skills to contribute to the community.

PROJECT STRENGTH AND LIMITATIONS

This QI project was implemented based on a community health needs assessment that was conducted by a local hospital (St. Francis Medical Center, 2019). Some of the strengths of this project include conducting this project in the community using local community resources such as a TTS that trained PCs and a faith-based location where the training was conducted in addition to ability of the project to train the trainers to lead multiple SCSGs as needed. The availability of Spanish translators and training materials in both languages, English and Spanish, was another strength. Consistent with this project, the use of community members as PC has been noted to help with health-related behavior change and increased social support in high risk communities (Gaber et al., 2020).

Project limitations included small sample size as it was difficult to get referrals and recruit smokers considering the COVID-19 pandemic. Attrition of the number of PCs over the course of the training, contributed to the small sample size of PCs. A larger sample size would have allowed running inferential statistics for data analysis and would have increased the generalizability of the findings (Littler, 2015).

FUTURE IMPLICATIONS FOR PRACTICE

Increasing smoking cessation rates is considered a top priority and continues to be the highest preventative initiative in the US (US Department of Health and Human Service, 2020). Although there is an abundance of research related to best practices for quitting smoking, a high prevalence of smoking and lower quit rates among individuals from high risk-communities remain significant (USDHHS, 2020). Using local community resources and hiring PCs of ethnic backgrounds representative to the community combined with evidence-based strategies followed in this project can increase the effectiveness of PC training programs and SCSGs. Such training programs can also offer ample opportunities to PCs to become certified TTSs to train more trainers.

Although increased opportunities for peer-led smoking cessation programs in high-risk communities are much needed, there are barriers to their success such as the recruitment process and unforeseen challenges such as the global pandemic. Overcoming such barriers can facilitate conducting such community programs.

In support of evidence, future projects should consider limiting time breaks between the PC training and smoker recruitment to avoid attrition of PCs which occurred during this project (Ngugi et al., 2018). Effective communication between coordinators of such a project and local community agencies and educating the community about the program can be effective in avoiding scheduling conflicts to give more opportunities for recruitment and participation (Kimes, Golden, Maynor, Spangler, & Bell, , 2014). Most notably, future efforts should include lengthening the time frame allowed for the development and implementation of the peer-led SCSG.

High risk, underserved communities may have a significant number of homelessness; homeless individuals are disproportionately affected by smoking and have higher rates of smoking prevalence within their environment (Pratt et al., 2019). Quitting smoking for homeless individuals was reported to have more barriers as they have a lower motivation to quit and more days with mental health problems; therefore, there may be a need for homeless-specific social services (Businelle, Cuate, Kesh, Poonawalla, & Kendzor, 2013). Homeless smokers near shelters experience higher levels of irritability, frustration/anger, stress and overall negative effect post-quitting even after accounting for nicotine withdrawal, daily smoking status, and socio-demographics (Reitzel et al., 2014). Although the effects of peer coaching amongst homeless smokers with substance abuse have shown positive results, PCs have experienced challenges in their role (Miler, Carver, Foster, & Parkes, 2020). Future research must be considered to develop strategies to overcome these barriers and challenges.

In 2010, the Affordable Care Act (ACA) included Medicare initiatives designed to improve care coordination services. Coordination improves gaps in care and improves health outcomes (Congdon, Eldridge, & Hoai-An, 2013). Future peer-led SCSG programs in high-risk communities may consider integrating care coordination to help with obtaining smoking cessation medications, transportation, referrals to local agencies, and other issues that arise (Congdon et al., 2013). Ensuring participants obtain smoking cessation medication prior to starting the peer-led SCSG was an important factor identified in the project and is known to improve smoking quit rates (Tibuakuu et al., 2019).

This project was unique in the availability of a TTS who was from the local community which may create difficulties in replicating the project. However, using community residents to assist in recruitment efforts may help in future projects, which may benefit from examining the effects of using a non-TTS trainer compared to a TTS trainer.

The disparity in smoking and quit rates in high-risk communities warrants the need for additional research aimed at specific interventions that address factors that impact this community.

Peer-led strategies can be cost effective and may offer more benefits in high-risk communities in regards to health behavior change (Ford et al., 2013; Petosa & Smith, 2014). Additionally, gaps between quality improvement projects and research can hinder efforts aimed at improving health care (Hirschhorn et al., 2018). It is recommended that QI projects partner with researchers to speed up necessary changes and improve the generalizability of the findings (Hirschhorn et al., 2018).

CONCLUSION

Research has shown that quitting smoking increases the smoker's life expectancy and reduces their risk of death (Jha et al., 2013). Although many smokers, who are motivated to quit, seek medical help, more than half of physicians do not respond to those needs due to lack of time and resources (Danesh et al., 2014; King, Dube, Babb, & McAfee, 2013; Bartsch, Härter, Niedrich, Brütt, & Buchholz, 2016; Van Eerd et al., 2017).

This QI project was able to successfully develop, implement, and evaluate a peer-led SCSG in a high-risk community. This purpose was accomplished in four phases; recruitment of PCs, training of PCs, recruitment of smokers, and the peer-led SCSG. The project faced unforeseen challenges due to the COVID-19 global pandemic which had delayed conducting the project and interfered with the recruitment process. However, with modifications, the project was able to continue training PCs and to recruit a small number of smokers for the SCSG. This project has created ample opportunities for successful peer incorporation into the health care team, which is feasible especially with increased reimbursement opportunities for preventative education.

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APPENDIX A

DATABASE SEARCH TOPICS

Terms	Limiters	Titles Retrieved and Reviewed	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
Smoking Cessation AND Peer Mentors	Peer Reviewed, English, Publication Date 2013-2020	CINAHL 2/2 PubMed 0 Cochrane Library 1 Web of Science 7/7	CINAHL 6/6 PubMed 0 Cochrane Library 1 Web of Science 7/7	CINAHL 3 PubMed 0 Cochrane Library 0 Web of Science 1
Smoking Cessation And Support Group	Peer Reviewed, English, Publication Date 2013-2020, Adults	CINAHL 35/35 PubMed 12 Cochrane Library 42 Web of Science 120	CINAHL 0 PubMed 12 Cochrane Library 1 Web of Science 5	CINAHL 0 PubMed 0 Cochrane Library 1 Web of Science 0
Smoking Cessation And Social Support	Peer Reviewed, English, Publication Date 2013-2020, Adults	CINAHL 107/107 PubMed 18 Cochrane Library 9 Web of Science 81	CINAHL 10 PubMed 2 Cochrane Library 9 Web of Science 8	CINAHL 10 PubMed 0 Cochrane 0 Web of Science 8

APPENDIX B**IMMIGRATION CENTER LETTER OF PERMISSION**

Helping Immigrant Families Establish Self-Sufficient Lives!

September 29, 2019

Rachel Jones
Southern California CSU DNP Consortium
California State University, Fullerton 800 N. State College Blvd.
Fullerton, CA 92831

RE: Peer-Led Smoking Cessation Support Group

The purpose of this letter of agreement is to show our support of your peer-led smoking cessation support group as a part of her Doctor of Nursing Practice education. After careful review of the above referenced proposal, your project may begin following Institutional Review Board determination at California State University, Fullerton. Contingent on CSUF approval, you will be granted access to work with clients as needed. No identifiable client data may be used during the completion of this project. In addition, you may not remove any physical form of data from the facility. When findings are disseminated as part of your project write-up or related presentations, you will not identify New Voice.

If there are any substantial changes to your protocol or procedures, a new project proposal must be submitted for approval. A final report is expected upon completion of the project. If any project activities continue one year after approval, a brief progress report should be submitted for ongoing approval.

APPENDIX C
READINESS RULER

APPENDIX D
COMMUNITY REFERRAL

**New Voice Immigration
Service**

Community Referral Form

Reason for Referral: _____

Name of Referring Program: _____

Address: _____

Name of Contact Person: _____

Phone: _____

Referral to:

Name of Program: _____

Address: _____

Name of Contact Person: _____

Phone: _____

Date : _____

APPENDIX F
PEER COACH EVALUATION

Leader Name: _____

Support Group Leader Evaluation

Criteria	Effective	Ineffective	N/A
Introduction			
Did the leader introduce themselves and the Co-Leader?			
Communication			
Did the Leader:			
Use Motivational Interviewing as opportunities were present?			
Try to establish rapport with participants?			
Use eye contact with participants?			
Use effective listening?			
Use effective body language?			
Use transitions between participants?			
Include all participants in discussions?			
Redirect sidebar conversations?			
Display compassion?			
Closing			
Did the leader recap the discussions points?			
Did the leader emphasized the progress made and provide encouragement?			

APPENDIX G

MULTIDIMENSIONAL SCALE OF PERCEIVED SOCIAL SUPPORT

Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (Zimet, Dahlem, Zimet & Farley, 1988)

Instructions: We are interested in how you feel about the following statements. Read each statement carefully. Indicate how you feel about each statement.

Circle the "1" if you Very Strongly Disagree
 Circle the "2" if you Strongly Disagree
 Circle the "3" if you Mildly Disagree
 Circle the "4" if you are Neutral
 Circle the "5" if you Mildly Agree
 Circle the "6" if you Strongly Agree
 Circle the "7" if you Very Strongly Agree

1.	There is a special person who is around when I am in need.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	SO
2.	There is a special person with whom I can share my joys and sorrows.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	SO
3.	My family really tries to help me.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Fam
4.	I get the emotional help and support I need from my family.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Fam
5.	I have a special person who is a real source of comfort to me.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	SO
6.	My friends really try to help me.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Fri
7.	I can count on my friends when things go wrong.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Fri
8.	I can talk about my problems with my family.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Fam
9.	I have friends with whom I can share my joys and sorrows.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Fri
10.	There is a special person in my life who cares about my feelings.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	SO
11.	My family is willing to help me make decisions.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Fam
12.	I can talk about my problems with my friends.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Fri

The items tended to divide into factor groups relating to the source of the social support, namely family (Fam), friends (Fri) or significant other (SO).

APPENDIX H

SMOKING CESSATION SUPPORT GROUP FLYER

The flyer features a central image of a hand holding a lit cigarette, with a pair of scissors positioned to cut it. The background is dark, and the text is in white and orange. The overall design is clean and professional.

Smoking Cessation
Free Classes and Weekly Support

Tuesdays
7:00 p.m. - 8:30 p.m.
Feb 25 to May 12

 LYNGATE CHURCH

GET THE HELP YOU NEED

For more information contact us at:

 new-voice
Immigration Assistance Services

10701 Sampson Ave. • Lynwood CA 90262 • 662-788-7665
www.new-voice.org

